

FORMING UNIVERSITY STUDENTS' FOREIGN LANGUAGE COMPETENCE THROUGH PERSONALITY APPROACH

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Abstract: *The article is devoted to the development of students' foreign language competence based on a personality-oriented approach in higher education. This approach takes into account the individual needs, interests and motivation of students, which contributes to improving the effectiveness of learning. Researchers such as L. Khokhlenkova, I. Yakimanskaya, and S. Kuklina emphasize its importance in the development of independence, creative thinking, and the ability to collaborate. The paper presents a system of tasks that includes five stages of mastering skills based on the book "The Catcher in the Rye". These stages cover understanding, application, transformation, communicative interaction and creative activity, providing comprehensive language learning. As a result, a personality-oriented approach contributes not only to the mastery of a foreign language, but also to the personal growth of students.*

Key words: *personality-oriented approach, foreign language competence, higher education, creative thinking, personal development.*

In the sphere of higher education, the acquisition of foreign language competence is crucial for academic and professional success. Approaches to teaching foreign language competence have changed significantly over the past decades, and among them, special attention is paid to a personality-oriented approach. This approach is focused on the individual needs, interests and motivation of students, which is meant you to create effective learning strategies and increase overall motivation to learn a language. The article is devoted to the formation of students' foreign language competence based on a personality-oriented approach.

In the process of studying the issues of a personality-oriented approach in education, special attention was paid to the works of L. Khokhlenkova, N. Sedakova, S. Kuklina, I. Yakimanskaya, E. Polat, O. Olekhnik, etc., Scholars highlight this approach as a primary strategy in higher professional education, outlining how foreign language teachers focus on students' personal development through pedagogical interaction as an integral educational system.

M. Akopova stresses that personality-oriented education fosters **self-education, self-determination, independence, and self-realization** for both teachers and students. This highlights the reciprocal nature of education, where both parties—teacher and student—are active participants in the process [1, p. 310].

I. Yakimanskaya considers a personality-oriented approach as recognition of **the individuality, identity, self-esteem** of each person, his development not as a "collective subject", but primarily as an individual [2, p. 28].

S. Kuklina believes that a personality-oriented approach has great personal development potential and ensures the development of such personality qualities as **the ability to work in collaboration, the ability to work independently and creative thinking**.

Following the views of S. Kuklina, in our article, the personality-oriented approach is considered as a teaching method that takes into account students' individual characteristics, fosters their independence, creative thinking, and collaboration skills, and creates conditions for their personal growth and self-fulfillment.

The application of the principles of differentiated learning in the process of learning English will set a new standard of quality in the formation of professional foreign language communicative competence of students [3].

This article presents a structured approach to language learning through a complex of assignments designed to cater to individual needs, interests, and motivations. Each of the five stages is characterized by the use of educational technologies and the selection of tasks that correspond to the goals and objectives of each specific stage. This article explores the use of Gaming technology and Case studies. The system of assignments is based on five steps of language skills: step 1- information block of assignment; step 2- application block of assignment; step 3- transformation block of assignment; step 4 - communicative block of assignment; step 5- creative block of assignment [4]. For this methodological manual was chosen book "The Catcher in the Rye" by J. D. Salinger [5]. The exercises of each unit of the manual are built according to the similar structure:

Step I: Information Block of Assignments. The first step enables students to show their comprehension and mastery in the field of study, particularly when engaging with textual material. Students are expected to read, comprehend, and absorb information pertaining to lexical units. Students do the following exercises. Among them:

Assignment 1. Warming-up activities: discussion questions.

1. How do small rituals or routines impact our perceptions of special occasions, like the Saturday night steak dinner at Pencey?

Assignment 2. Read the text and learn the new words used in the text.

Assignment 3. Pay attention to the following vocabulary notes.

1. Racket - (noun) a dishonest or fraudulent scheme or activity; a fraudulent or dishonest business operation.

Assignment 4. Learn the definition of the active vocabulary.

By engaging in these activities, students can develop their understanding of the text's vocabulary and concepts, thereby improving their overall comprehension and reading proficiency.

Step II. Application Block of Assignments. This step empowers students to apply their knowledge and understanding, crucial for enhancing language competencies. Students should be prepared to employ the vocabulary they have acquired in their prepared speech. The following exercises are offered:

Assignment 1. Match the active words to their meanings.

1. Horsing around	a) to focus one's attention or mental effort on a particular object or activity.
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Assignment 2. Fill in the gaps with the active word vocabulary.

1. It looked pretty as hell, and we all started throwing snowballs and _____ all over the place. 2. The thing that was _____ about it, though, was that he had poems written all over the fingers and the pocket and everywhere.

Assignment 3. Paraphrase the italicized part of each sentence choosing the appropriate phrase from the list:

(*Racket, Lumpy, Monotonous, Fiend, Psychoanalyze, Leukemia, Halitosis*)

1. What a *scheme*. You should've seen the steaks. 2. You always got these very *uneven* mashed potatoes on steak night, and for dessert you got Brown Betty, which nobody ate, except maybe the little kids in the lower school that didn't know any better and guys like Ackley that ate everything.

Through these activities, students can practice incorporating newly learned vocabulary into their speech, thereby solidifying their understanding and ability to use language effectively in practical situations.

Step III. Transformation block of assignments. The third group of tasks includes transformational exercises that involve transferring the model to other

models. The purpose of this step is to develop students' ability to analyze text, apply the acquired knowledge and skills to transform information and create new models. The exercises are as follows:

Assignment 1. Put the events in the chronological order.

a	b	c	d	e	f

1. Holden reminisces about his brother Allie and decides to write the composition about Allie's baseball mitt, which is filled with poems.

2. Back at the dorm, Brossard looks for a bridge game while Ackley monopolizes Holden's room, talking incessantly.

3. After dinner, Holden and his friends enjoy playing in the snow outside the dormitory.

Assignment 2. Define the problems of the characters in the text:

Character A- Mal Brossard

Character B- Allie Caulfield

Assignment 3. Find some possible solutions for the above mentioned problems.

Assignment 4. Questions for discussion: discuss the following question:

1. What would you do if you were served a disappointing meal like the steak dinner described at Pencey?

Assignment 5. Write your own judgments of about the attitudes of the characters to each other.

A- Holden's attitude towards Stradlater, Ackley, Mal Brossard

By engaging in transformational exercises and discussions, students can enhance their analytical skills, deepen their understanding of the text's themes and characters, and develop problem-solving abilities.

Step IV. Communicative block of assignments. This stage aids students in expanding their ability to use English as a tool for communication. Learners can show and enhance their skills by exchanging information, ideas, problems and solutions. So, for these step the following exercises are appropriate:

Assignment 1. Make up your own plan of the story.

Assignment 2. Discuss the plan with your groupmates in groups.

Assignment 3. Retell the text according to your plan to your group.

Assignment 4. Describe characters in the text:

a) appearance b) actions c) attitude to other characters d) background

Assignment 5. Answer the following comprehension question.

1. Why does the protagonist believe Pencey serves steak on Saturday nights?

Assignment 6. Think up a dialogue between Holden and Allie and dramatize it.

Through group discussions, comprehension questions, and interactive activities, students can improve their ability to communicate in English, express their thoughts clearly, and engage in meaningful dialogue about the text.

Step V. Creative block of assignments. The final step encourages students to express themselves creatively using the language. This could involve tasks such as writing a summary or short stories, creating dialogues or participating in role-playing performances. The exercises are as follows:

Assignment 1. Write your own ending of the story.

Assignment 2. Write a short summary of the story.

Assignment 3. Get ready for the role-play.

Role-play scenario: Holden Caulfield has just finished writing a composition for his roommate, Stradlater. The composition is about Holden's late brother Allie's baseball mitt, which was covered in poems written in green ink. Stradlater returns to the room and asks about the composition.

Assignment 5. Write a short essay on one of the following topics (150-200 words).

By participating in creative tasks like dialogue creation and story writing, students can open their creativity, practice using English in diverse ways and develop their language skills in a fun and engaging manner.

The use of gaming technologies and case studies offers an effective approach to the development of foreign language competence among students. Using various tasks similar to role-playing, dialogue, analysis and problem solving, students can develop the necessary skills, such as communication and cognitive.

To sum up, the personality-oriented approach in foreign language education develops both language skills and personal growth. Through a combination of informational, application, transformational, communicative, and creative assignments, students engage effectively with the language, enhancing critical thinking, collaboration. This methodological approach to teaching foreign languages based on J.D. Salinger's "The Catcher in the Rye" offers valuable resources for educators. It promotes individual learning, develops communication skills, uses a structured approach, uses real-life scenarios and stimulates creativity.

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